

Resummation Scales and the Assessment of Theoretical Uncertainties in Parton Distribution Functions ^a

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We discuss perturbative solutions of renormalization group equations, and propose the use of resummation scale techniques in assessing theoretical uncertainties on the extraction of parton distribution functions from data.

Many applications of Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) to precision calculations for high-energy collider physics involve the perturbative solution of renormalization group equations (RGEs). It has long been known that, at any given order of perturbation theory, the differences between RGE solutions obtained by methods which are equivalent up to formally subleading orders provide a significant source of theoretical uncertainty on predictions for physical observables.

In the literature of calculations based on QCD resummation, these uncertainties are commonly taken into account by a variety of different techniques, which appeal to the principle of introducing so-called resummation scales, of the order of the hard momentum-transfer scale of the process but otherwise arbitrary, and setting criteria to let them vary and evaluate the corresponding variation in the theoretical prediction.

In several other common applications of QCD to collider physics, on the other hand, resummation scale variations are not performed. A notable example is the determination of parton distribution functions (PDFs) from global fits to experimental data,^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7} central to virtually any aspect of hadron collider physics. In this application, RGEs and their perturbative solutions are used for the evolution of the PDFs themselves and for the evolution of the running coupling. The fact that RGE theory uncertainties are not included and resummation scale variations are not performed leads to an underestimate of the uncertainties associated with the extraction of PDFs from global fits to data.

This point is illustrated in detail in our recent work⁸. There, we discuss various aspects of theory uncertainties from RGE perturbative solutions and propose resummation scale methods to characterize them. Applying this to deep-inelastic scattering (DIS) structure functions, we show that resummation scale effects are significant in kinematic regions relevant to PDF determinations. In this article we summarize some of the results from Ref.⁸.

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We consider RGE of the general form

$$\frac{d \ln R}{d \ln \mu}(\mu, \alpha_s(\mu)) = \gamma(\alpha_s(\mu)), \quad (1)$$

where R is a renormalized quantity, function of the strong coupling α_s and renormalization scale μ , and γ is its anomalous dimension, computable as a power series expansion in the coupling α_s .

In Ref.⁸ we examine several examples, at next-to-leading (NLO) and next-to-next-to-leading (NNLO) order, and analyze RGE solutions obtained by methods which differ by subleading-order terms.^b To characterize the differences between such solutions, we introduce the evolution operator G which connects R at two scales μ and μ_0 , $R_\mu = G(\mu, \mu_0)R_{\mu_0}$, and trace the differences between solutions back to the fact that, due to subleading orders, one has, for a given μ' , $G(\mu, \mu_0) \neq G(\mu, \mu')G(\mu', \mu_0)$. We refer to this as *perturbative hysteresis*⁸.

For the application to PDF evolution, R in Eq. (1) is to be thought of as the flavor multiplet of PDF Mellin moments, and γ as the Mellin transform of DGLAP splitting functions. Besides, one has an RGE of the form (1) for the running coupling, in which R is proportional to the coupling α_s , and γ to the QCD β function. Hysteresis effects in both these RGEs are analyzed quantitatively in Ref.⁸.

The extraction of PDFs $f_j(x, \mu)$ from collider data uses factorization formulas relating f_j to physical observables Σ , e.g. DIS structure functions, with the schematic form

$$\Sigma(x, Q) = \sum_j \int dz H_j(z, Q, \alpha_s(\mu_R), \mu_F) f_j(x/z, \mu_F), \quad (2)$$

where H_j are perturbatively computable hard-scattering functions, μ_F is the factorization scale, and μ_R is the renormalization scale. Standard QCD calculations estimate theoretical uncertainties associated with unknown higher orders in Eq. (2) by setting criteria for variations of the scales μ_F and μ_R .

Ref.⁸ observes that theoretical uncertainties on the extraction of PDFs arise both from μ_F and μ_R variations in Eq. (2) and from unknown higher orders in the kernels γ in Eq. (1), and proposes to take the latter into account by resummation scale techniques. To this end, two different but essentially equivalent methods are formulated. One is based on expressing the evolution operator G via the analytic formalism of g -functions,⁸ which is frequently applied in soft-gluon resummation calculations. Schematically, at the k -th order of logarithmic accuracy $N^k\text{LL}$, this is of the form

$$G^{N^k\text{LL}} \sim g_0^{N^k\text{LL}}(\lambda) \exp \left[\sum_{l=0}^k \alpha_s^l(\mu) g_{l+1}(\lambda) \right], \quad \lambda \sim \alpha_s(\mu) \beta_0 \ln(\mu^{(\text{Res})}/\mu), \quad (3)$$

where the g 's are perturbatively computable functions of the scaling variable λ , and μ_{Res} is the resummation scale. Explicit expressions for the g -functions up to $k = 3$ are given in Ref.¹². Another method is based on displacing the argument of the coupling appearing in the perturbative expansion of γ , so as to obtain a new effective anomalous dimension differing from the previous one by subleading terms. This method is well-suited for numerical evaluations. In either method, one ends up introducing resummation scales $\mu_{\text{PDF}}^{(\text{Res})}$ for the PDF evolution and $\mu_{\alpha_s}^{(\text{Res})}$ for the coupling evolution.

As an application, we illustrate the case in which we take Σ in Eq. (2) to be the DIS structure function $F_2(x, Q)$. We perform variations of renormalization and factorization scales, μ_R and μ_F , and of resummation scales, which we parameterize as $\mu_{\alpha_s}^{(\text{Res})} = \xi_{\alpha_s} Q$ and $\mu_{\text{PDF}}^{(\text{Res})} = \xi_{\text{PDF}} Q$. Fig. 1

^bThe examples considered in Ref.⁸ are single-logarithmic resummation problems. Similar effects in double-logarithmic Sudakov problems have been observed e.g. in Refs.^{9,10,11}.

Figure 1 – The structure function F_2 from Ref. ⁸ versus x , at NLO and NNLO in perturbation theory, with the uncertainty bands associated with variations of renormalization and factorization scales, μ_R and μ_F , and resummation scale parameters ξ_{α_s} and ξ_{PDF} . We use MSHT20 PDFs at $Q_0 = 2$ GeV and $\alpha_s(M_Z) = 0.118$ as RGE inputs.

shows results at NLO (left panel) and NNLO (right panel). Resummation scale uncertainties are observed to be generally non-negligible with respect to the renormalization and factorization scale uncertainties in the kinematic region considered. In the left hand side panel, we see that the effect of the resummation scale parameter ξ_{PDF} dominates the low- x region while the effect of the factorization scale μ_F dominates at the largest x . The right hand side panel illustrates that the size of the uncertainty bands is reduced at NNLO. The behavior above reflects higher-order corrections to F_2 at small x being dominated by flavor-singlet quark anomalous dimensions. ^{13,14}

The results shown in Fig. 1 are for $Q = 10$ GeV. The importance of resummation scale effects, relative to that of renormalization and factorization scale effects, increases with Q (and is eventually becoming relevant for increasing x). To illustrate the behavior of the uncertainty bands with varying Q , in Fig. 2 we plot the Q -dependence of the relative variation $\Delta F_2/F_2$. The ξ_{PDF} contribution starts from zero and grows rapidly with Q , remaining sizeable out to large Q while the μ_F contribution is largest at low Q and decreases with increasing Q . Analogously, the μ_R contribution is important at low Q and decreases with Q , while the ξ_{α_s} is subdominant at low Q but becomes relevant at high Q .

The above numerical results indicate that RGE uncertainties are relevant in kinematical regions which influence current and forthcoming PDF extractions. They will also be relevant in regions explored at future lepton-hadron colliders ^{15,16}. As the ξ_{PDF} contribution remains significant at large Q , RGE uncertainties are important for high-scale PDF probes such as very energetic jets and top quarks.

To conclude, we note that the method we have described can be used in processes sensitive to collinear as well as transverse momentum dependent (TMD) ¹⁷ distributions. It will be applicable in extractions both of PDF and of TMD.

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Figure 2 – Q -dependence of the relative variation $\Delta F_2/F_2$ for $x = 10^{-2}$ (top) and $x = 10^{-3}$ (bottom), at NLO (left) and NNLO (right), associated with variations of renormalization and factorization scales, μ_R and μ_F , and resummation scale parameters ξ_{α_s} and ξ_{PDF} .

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